

D6.1 Market analysis and initial business models

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Authors

Authors in alphabetical order		
Name	Organisation	Email
Matteo Andolfi	NXW	m.andolfi@nextworks.it
Edoardo Bonetto	LINKS	edoardo.bonetto@linksfoundation.com
Manuel Fuentes	5COMM	manuel.fuentes@fivecomm.eu
Miriam Ortiz	5COMM	miriam.ortiz@fivecomm.eu
George Karagiannopoulos	HIT	g.karagiannopoulos@hit-innovations.com
Dimitris Klondis	UBI	dklonidis@ubitech.eu
Eirini Liotou	ICCS	eirini.liotou@iccs.gr
Theodoros Rokkas	INC	trokkas@incites.eu
Peter Schmitting	FSCOM	Peter.schmitting@fscom.fr
Andrea Suarez Garcia	VICOM	asuarez@vicomtech.org
Rudolf Sušnik	ININ	rudolf.susnik@iinstitute.eu
Marios Zinonos	HIT	m.zinonos@hit-innovations.com

Control sheet

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
5GAA	5G Automotive Association
6G-IA	6G Infrastructure Association
AF	Application Function
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOEP	Automotive Open Experimental Platform
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DL	Download
DML	Distributed Machine Learning
DMP	Digital Management Plan
EaaS	Experimentation as a Service
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FL	Federated Learning
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HD	High Definition
HW	Hardware
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IMT	International Mobile Telecommunications
IT	Information Technology
ITU	International Telecommunication Union

KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCM	Lifecycle Management
LTE	Long Term Evolution
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
NF	Network Function
NGBR	Non-Guaranteed Bit Rate
OBU	On Board Unit
RAM	Random Access Memory
RAN	Radio Access Network
RSU	Road Side Unit
SA	Stand Alone
SC	Steering Committee
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SW	Software
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
UL	Upload
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VR	Virtual Reality
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The aim of this deliverable is to provide details about the 5G-IANA ecosystem along with the initial envisioned business model for the 5G-IANA platform. In addition, to provide the results of a survey that was conducted with the scope to collect the expectations that third parties have from the 5G-IANA platform¹. The roles around the 5G-IANA platform have been identified, and the interactions among them have been presented in the reference model that has been created. The incentives for participating in the 5G-IANA platform has been identified for all the roles in in the ecosystem.

A review of business models that were used in past FIRE projects that had developed experimental platforms has been performed to identify the best practices and lessons learned that could be adopted for the 5G-IANA platform. Bases on that information, the initial business model for the 5G-IANA model has been presented. The main offering is the Experimentation as a Service and the supporting activities such as consulting and training service to experimenters.

A survey was created and conducted online in order to capture the expectations that third parties have from the 5G-IANA platform. The survey was broadly communicated to possible experimenters and relevant stakeholders and a total of 23 responses have been captured. One of the most important remarks is that the majority of the participants are interested in open Virtual AFs and NFs, which stresses the need for providing reusable functions.

¹ *Note: The scope of this deliverable has been reoriented as per the project's interim review (June 2022), so as to move from a purely state-of-the-art market analysis (as anticipated by the DoA) to a study that aims to identify the expectations of third parties from the 5G-IANA AOEP platform. The feedback from this survey will be therefore a useful input for the project-wide activities towards developing an attractive platform and towards engaging external SMEs to experiment on top of it.*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. 5G-IANA concept and approach

5G-IANA aims at providing an open 5G experimentation platform, on top of which third party experimenters, i.e., Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the Automotive-related 5G-PPP vertical will have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services. An Automotive Open Experimental Platform (AOEP) will be specified, as the whole set of hardware and software resources that provides the computational and communication/transport infrastructure as well as the management and orchestration components, coupled with an enhanced nApp Toolkit tailored to the Automotive sector. 5G-IANA will expose to experimenters secured and standardized Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for facilitating all the different steps towards the production stage of a new service. 5G-IANA will target different virtualization technologies integrating different Management and Orchestration (MANO) frameworks for enabling the deployment of the end-to-end network services across different domains (vehicles, road infrastructure, Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) nodes and cloud resources). 5G-IANA nApp toolkit will be linked with a new Automotive Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) Repository including an extended list of ready to use open accessible Automotive-related VNFs and nApp templates, that will form a repository for SMEs to use and develop new applications. Finally, 5G-IANA will develop a Distributed Artificial Intelligence / Machine Learning (AI/ML) (DML) framework, that will provide functionalities for simplified management and orchestration of collections of AI/ML service components and will allow ML-based applications to penetrate the Automotive world, due to its inherent privacy preserving nature. 5G-IANA will be demonstrated through 7 Automotive-related use cases in 2 5G Stand Alone (SA) testbeds. Moving beyond technological challenges, and exploiting input from the demonstration activities, 5G-IANA will perform a multi-stakeholder cost-benefit analysis that will identify and validate market conditions for innovative, yet sustainable business models supporting a long-term roadmap towards the pan-European deployment of 5G as key advanced Automotive services enabler.

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

The objectives of this deliverable are the following: to identify the ecosystem that will interact with the 5G-IANA Automotive Open Experimental Platform

(AOEP), to define the initial business plan for the service provisioning of the AOEP, and to identify the expectations of third parties from the AOEP.

This deliverable presents the work undertaken in T6.1: Market research and actor-role analysis, enriched though as described below.

The deliverable has the following structure:

- In section 2 the ecosystem around the 5G-IANA platform is presented: the roles and the actors are defined along with their interactions. The main incentives for each of the actors to participate in the AOEP are presented. In addition, the initial business model envisioned for the AOEP is presented.
- In section 3 a review of business models used in other experimental platforms (FIRE projects) along with the initial business model for the 5G-IANA platform are presented.
- In section 4 the results of an online survey regarding third party expectations from the AOEP are presented.

The scope of this deliverable has been reoriented as per the project's interim review (June 2022), so as to move from a purely state-of-the-art market analysis (as anticipated by the DoA) to a study that aims to identify the expectations of third parties from the 5G-IANA AOEP platform. The feedback from this survey will be therefore a useful input for the project-wide activities towards developing an attractive platform and towards engaging external SMEs to experiment on top of it. Moreover, the deliverable has been enriched so as to include the project's devised plan for third party experimentation.

1.3. Intended audience

The dissemination level of D6.1 is 'public' (PU) and available to members of the consortium, the European Commission (EC) Services and those external to the Project. This document is intended to serve as a guideline and reference for all 5G-IANA beneficiaries regarding the expectations from third parties, the same information can also be used by facilitators of similar experimental platforms.

2. 5G-IANA ECOSYSTEM

In the ICT sector, the rise of the Over The Top (OTT) players has shown, in the last years, the prominent role that Platform-based business models can have in the market. Some of the biggest companies are built around platform-based business models and experience higher valuations than other businesses with other business models.

Big cloud providers or hyperscalers (e.g., Amazon, Google, Microsoft, etc.) have been among top business players in past years and they continue to remain such. Starting by hosting general IT applications, they have also taken the advantage of their cloud computing capabilities by expanding their portfolios with their own offers of private 5G, and most have also completed strategic acquisitions and hired from the mobile industry [1]. Thus, they have become important players in 5G field and therefore they cannot be neglected within the discussion on actors with potential impact to the market addressed by 5G-IANA. Although the biggest cloud players are not EU companies, it must be anyway added that certain stake of the cloud services market has been also adopted by multiple (EU-based) network operators providing their own infrastructure for both their own services and for third parties hosted services as well.

In particular, MNOs are quite significantly able to capitalize their cloud infrastructures on the 5G Stand Alone (5G SA) network architecture which introduces Service-based Architecture and cloud-native functions. Advanced 5G functionalities such as Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC), utilizing on MNOs' wide geographical distribution of their infrastructure, give them even better opportunities compared to their competition having more centralised infrastructure. Although 80% of data processing takes place in centralized infrastructure today and 20% in smart connected objects, this ratio is expected to reverse over the next couple of years, thus shifting data processing paradigm from cloud-centric to cloud-continuum [2].

With the introduction of 5G, the number of verticals that are designed around platform-based business models is growing quickly. We expect that this growth will continue to exist and there will be a stronger connection between the verticals and the mobile ecosystems. In that new era there is a lack of experimental facilities in which developers can test their services before they bring it in the market. Since the automotive vertical is considered one of the most important for 5G and several Use Cases (UC) are examined, the need for an experimentation platform that provides all the necessary resources in order for experimenters to deploy and test their services is eminent. It is also

important to understand the new business model that will be formed around the experimental platforms like 5G-IANA.

The section describes all the relations and interactions among the different roles in the 5G-IANA ecosystem. This first step is very important towards the better understanding of the ecosystem and its characteristics and will help in the investigation of the associated business models around the 5G-IANA platform in the upcoming phases of the project.

Initially some concepts that are essential for the description of the ecosystem are presented, followed by the description of the different roles of the actors that participate in the ecosystem. The 5G-IANA platform has the central role in that ecosystem in order to examine the possible interactions that the different roles will have within that ecosystem. The section concludes with the initial business model for the 5G-IANA AOEP platform.

2.1. Actors and roles

In order to understand the business model around the 5G-IANA platform, it is important to capture how value is created in a complex system with a lot of interdependencies. In this analysis we will use the value network to describe all the inter relations within the ecosystem.

The following definitions are used in the following sections:

- **Actor:** an entity that participates in the business model, it can provide or consume services.
- **Role:** the functionality of each actor that participates in the business model. An actor can take one or more of the roles, while a role can be undertaken by several actors.
- **Relationship:** the interaction between two roles in the model.

This section provides an overview of the different roles that have been identified in the 5G-IANA ecosystem (the work has been made in WP6 but is also included in D2.1).

- **Mobile Network Operators (MNO):** they deploy and operate the telecommunication infrastructure that is required for connectivity (core and Radio Access Network - RAN). They own the physical equipment such as base stations, antennas, switches, etc.
- **Cloud Infrastructure Providers:** they provide all required storage, cloud computing and corresponding networking resources (CPUs, RAM, storage). These can be in a central (cloud location) or local location, in edge servers.

- **Road Infrastructure operators:** they are responsible for the deployment, operation, and maintenance of the road infrastructure. They can also own and operate road-side facilities such as ICT equipment, cameras and sensors located in the road networks.
- **HW Vendors:** they provide all type of hardware to all interested parties, for example base stations, antennas, switches, routers, servers, network cards, sensors, cameras, CPUs, RAM, Road-Side Units (RSU), On-Board Units (OBU), entertainment systems, etc.
- **SW vendors:** they provide all the necessary generic software that is required by all other parties. For example, the firmware that is required for the hardware devices, all type of software for the entertainment systems, etc. This role does not include the development and provision of nApps and Application and Network Functions (AFs/NFs).
- **Vehicle Manufacturers:** entities that are in charge of manufacturing all type of vehicles.
- **R&D:** research centres and academic institutions that are responsible for the development and testing of upcoming technologies and applications.
- **Service Creators:** all type of service creation entities such as SMEs, and software developers.
- **Service Providers:** they are responsible for providing the service to end users (for example Intelligent Driving, HD maps, etc.).
- **Application and Network Functions Developers:** they develop the Application Functions (AFs) and Network Functions (NFs) that can be used as building blocks for creating nApps.
- **Application and Network Functions Providers:** they are responsible for providing the AFs and NFs to be on-boarded through the functionalities provided by the nApp Toolkit platform component.
- **nApp Developers:** they are responsible for the development of nApps.
- **nApp Providers:** they are the ones that provide the nApps either to end users or service creators/providers.
- **End Users:** includes all type of users that are the recipients of the services. They can be individual users (B2C) or business customers (B2B). Some examples are vehicle owners, drivers, passengers or pedestrians for end users and transport operators, traffic management, freight and logistics, or providers of public services.

Evidently, a certain stakeholder in the emerging ecosystem may well hold more than one of these roles. Characteristic examples include Service Creators, who may be a SW Vendor; a nApp Provider can be a Service Provider; a nApp

Developer may be a SW Vendor. The identification and this fine-grained distinction between roles aim to highlight the focus areas and different specializations, not indicating necessarily the emergence of distinct stakeholders.

2.2. Incentives/Benefits for the different roles to use/participate in the platform

In 2021, the global telecom services market was valued at USD 1.75 trillion, and it is expected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 5.5% [3]. In 2020, the mobile data services segment held a share of about 33.0%, whereby Over-The-Top (OTT) channels are the customers' preferred option, offering video, audio, and other media content over the Internet [4]. 5G was and is developed based on the 2015 targets by the International Mobile Telecommunications-2000 (IMT-2000), which looked at potential future consumer demands and positioned them the three central trends of massive mobile broadband communications, massive machine type communications, and ultra-reliable low latency communications.

Figure 1: Usage scenarios of IMT-2000, source [5]

The three development trends were driven by a range of use cases, which were expected to push the future demand of mobile communication services [5],[6], such as:

- *healthcare* including telemedicine, connected ambulance with Augmented/Virtual Reality (AR/VR),
- *entertaining* including virtual reality events,
- *manufacturing*, including machine-to-machine (M2M) communication and remote robot control,
- *public safety*, including drone control and improved rescue services,

- etc.

The *automotive* sector with its potentially new services in remote vehicle maintenance, remote assistance of automated and autonomous driving, platooning, infotainment, update of high-definition (HD) map updates, etc., was also included as a sector driving the demand for novel solutions in future mobile communication systems such as 5G.

5G is standardized by the 3GPP [7], which introduced and still develops a range of new or updated 5G features to address the diverse needs of beforementioned new user groups. Key features [8] especially for the automotive sectors are:

- *Quality of Service (QoS)*: A user can have several QoS Flows in uplink (mobile phone to network) and downlink (mobile network to mobile phone). The standard distinguishes between two categories of QoS Flows:
 - *Guaranteed bit rate (GBR)* provides a guaranteed bit rate to a user, which is typically used for time sensitive applications such as voice, V2X, or real-time gaming. While GBR typically offers latencies in the order of 100ms, delay critical GBR QoS Flows may work in the order of 10ms.
 - Non-guaranteed bit rate (NGBR) is typically used for non-time sensitive applications, such as web browsing. In 3GPP TS 23.203 [9], section 6.1.7, a set of QoS Flow with specific packet forwarding behaviour were specified and are identified with a label called QoS class identifier (QCI). Two QCIs for V2X message exchange are already specified.
- *Network Slicing*: This allows the selection and allocation of mobile network resources isolated from other services to fit the requirements of a specific service. For instance, a network slice for steering of a vehicle remotely, radio resources can be allocated to guarantee a transmission of video from the vehicle to the remote driver with low latency and a guaranteed minimum latency.
- *Edge Computing*: Latency is critical for many automotive services. While still most delay occurs on the radio interface, the transmission latency between a base station and a server infrastructure can be reduced by locating the server infrastructure topologically close to the base station location. The end-user experience is both improved by the reduced latency, while also the network efficiency can improve by reducing the backhaul requirements.

Nowadays, cloud computing resources can be easily ordered and used. It is the aim that customer can easily commission a virtual mobile network resources with specified QoS, network slicing setting, and edge computing resources in the future. The 5G products, however, have not reached this maturity level, yet. It is this gap in the service creation and especially in the automotive vertical that 5G-IANA aims to tackle. By providing an open experimentation platform that will give access to 5G and automotive resources, third parties can have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services making a step closer to commercialization of their developments.

Testing new 5G use cases, features, and solutions before their commercial roll-out is a crucial aspect of innovation, since it identifies and resolves potential bottlenecks, while it is vital for large-scale rollout facilitation and mass adoption. Before release to the general public, service providers test M2M communication in a 5G testbed to understand and evaluate the performance of their application/solution/service in a real 5G radio environment and to accelerate end-user adoption.

The AOEP of 5G-IANA includes a set of hardware and software resources that provides the compute and communication/transport infrastructure, as well as the management and orchestration components, coupled with an enhanced nApp (Network Application) Toolkit, tailored to the Automotive industry. The toolkit's purpose is to provide ready-to-use building blocks that can serve the needs of multiple use cases. The 5G-IANA management and orchestration components and the nApp Toolkit expose to experimenters secured and standardized APIs for facilitating all the different steps towards the production stage of a new service. The 5G-IANA VNFs Repository integrates already existing 5G-PPP repositories of open-source VNFs. The 5G-IANA AOEP provides capabilities and functionalities for designing, validating and benchmarking Intelligent nApps and their components, as well as for monitoring and dynamically adapting them at run-time.

In this section the incentives or benefits for each of the different roles (that have identified in the ecosystem) to participate in the 5G-IANA platform are presented.

2.2.1. MNOs

The interaction with 5G-IANA platform can help MNOs to identify new market and business challenges, realize possible opportunities and early identify the new business models. In addition, it can help MNOs to enter the lucrative automotive market and to expand their portfolio of mobile applications and

services. By using the platform, they can get a better understanding of the automotive applications in their virtualized environment and may manage to deploy such applications faster in the future. The 5G-IANA platform can simplify the procedures of service provisioning and monitoring and can simplify access to network resources. With the tools included in the 5G-IANA platform, MNOs can gain advantage against competitors in applications such as logistics services and traffic management applications, which are essential for commercial success of 5G mobile network in the automotive vertical. The platform as an open and flexible environment can attract innovators to deploy their original ideas that would not be possible to the commercial network of an MNO, thus, they can establish new relations with actors from the automotive vertical and with new start-ups and experimenters. Finally, the participation in efforts like the 5G-IANA platform can give advantage to MNO's 5G network users as they would be able to quickly access new and advanced services.

2.2.2. Cloud Infrastructure providers

With regard to the 5G-IANA AOEP platform and potential use cases that the platform is suitable for support them, it is expected various cloud topologies (i.e., centric-oriented, cloud-continuum) would be suitable for hosting the platform and use cases, however, it would depend on certain requirements of the component/components hosted. The AOEP platform, as a central tool responsible for orchestrating the resources required for specific use case components onboarding, managing components life cycle, and providing resource monitoring tools among other functionalities, may not have such strict latency, round-trip time, and data throughput requirements as it would be a case for certain automotive nApps dealing with autonomous driving and related challenges. For implementing use cases with challenging requirements as already mentioned, cloud infrastructure providers with distributed infrastructure will most likely have certain advantage comparing to competitors utilizing cloud-centric infrastructure. Nevertheless, as long as service providers will provide services nation-wide, EU-wide or world-wide, it would be a must for cloud infrastructure providers to provide capable, reliable and secure inter-connections. The latter will be, for example, also demonstrated within UC #7.

Besides meeting the technical requirements necessary for successfully operating nApps/use cases, potential cloud infrastructure providers may further attract customers by providing a virtual environment customized for reducing deployment and operating costs, improving time to market, providing extensive resource and network monitoring tools, life cycle

management tools, etc. As it is obvious the 5G-IANA AOEP platform and nApps onboarded and managed over it cannot be realized without reliable cloud infrastructure support, and it is on cloud infrastructure providers how innovative they will be to advance from it.

2.2.3. Road Infrastructure providers

Road infrastructure providers will be one of the main beneficiaries of the 5G-IANA platform in the long term. The creation and adoption of new services in the automotive vertical will increase the safety in the roads and will allow them to provide new targeted services to their customers. In addition, the usage of their infrastructure during the experimentation phase can give them valuable information regarding any upgrades that need to be made to their infrastructure like for example the introduction of new RSUs that offer more capabilities than the existing equipment. The collaboration with third parties is considered essential since they can provide their expectations and requirements from the future 5G automotive applications that must be created.

2.2.4. HW Vendors

Vendors of mobile communication equipment and mobile operators observe very closely the mobile communication market and its evolving trends. While many technical features are standardized in 3GPP, vendors focus in their product development on those features where the markets indicate a growing and stable future demand and revenue. Similarly, mobile network operators emphasize in their 5G network rollout both areas and technical features which promise a solid return of investment. A strong demand by the automotive industry in products such as the 5G-IANA platform is also a strong indicator for both vendors and mobile operators to focus their 5G development plans accordingly.

With their participation in the 5G-IANA platform HW vendors will have the opportunity to promote their products through the platform and get in contact with potential customers that will participate in the experimentation phase. In addition, the utilization of equipment during the experiments can assist into the validation of their products in new applications and services and help them identify future improvements that need to be made to meet the new requirements. An additional benefit will be that they will increase their knowledge in techniques and technologies such as AI, ML, etc., while this engagement can provide useful insights on how they can add these advanced features in their upcoming products.

2.2.5. SW Providers

The user-oriented service management is one of the main trends in 5G, and a core feature in the design of 6G. The role here of the 5G-IANA platform is critical as it provides the missing link between the vertical end user domain and the network resource control and management layers expanding in general over multiple infrastructure domains from core to edge and even the extreme-edge.

The platform is designed in a fully modular approach and adopts open development principles. These two features essentially enable the growth of dedicated SW development teams that are focused on the development of platform solutions, expansions and interfaces. The key benefit of the modular approach is that different parts of the platform can be developed or extended independently of the other parts as long as the interfacing conditions are properly met. As an example, such parts may include: a) The nApp and component catalogue which may evolve into a marketplace repository with advance query features or adaptive catalogues for different vertical types, b) the application orchestration real time management logic which may be enhanced with advance analytics and monitoring features for automated end-user responses to application or network related changes, c) the slice management and resource handling mechanism that can be further adapted to different end-user domains, with extreme-edge or even swarm processing capabilities. Moreover, the open access feature enhances further the aforementioned capabilities providing a common seamless development environment allowing developers to focus easily on specific development features while reusing common and well-established platform parts.

Platform SW providers originate typically from the vendors as providers of supporting control and management solutions. However, with the 5G-IANA platform solution, independent SW platform providers (e.g., SMEs) may provide dedicated solutions tailored to different vertical sectors or even advance add-ons to the platform (e.g., to orchestrate where resources for AI-based applications). Furthermore, the adoption of the overall 5G-IANA application deployment and management model directly by a service or telecom provider offers the capability to the later to expand their range of services directly to the end users (e.g., focusing especially on private 5G end users).

It is important to note that there are no standards specifically related to the application-level management, and these are expected to start emerging as technology moves towards 6G. This indicates a good opportunity for platforms like 5G-IANA to promote their features and benefits to the broader developer's

community and infrastructure management stakeholders, exposing the alternative market opportunities that it offers.

2.2.6. Vehicle manufacturers

Emerging trends like shared mobility and autonomous driving are expected to disrupt the traditional business model of car sales. In this highly competitive landscape, vehicle manufacturers will have to compete with new players as other actors in the ecosystem such as SW and HW vendors are targeting the automotive vertical customer segment. The predictions estimate \$100billion for data connectivity services such as apps, navigation, entertainment, remote services, and service upgrades. The introduction of 5G promises to bridge two distinct until recently worlds: that of telecommunications and vehicle manufacturers. The participation in 5G-IANA platform will give car manufacturers increased knowledge and interaction with players outside their current ecosystem increasing their competitive advantage. By providing their vehicle to the platform they can take a look at the new services that expected to enter the market the next years and thus plan their moves accordingly. The results from the executed experiments can help them understand the requirements for running the new services and thus modify the HW and SW in their cars in order to be ready when the applications enter the market.

2.2.7. Application, network function and network application developers (nApp developers)

nApp developers can benefit from the usage of the 5G-IANA platform in all the phases of the software development cycle, starting from the design up to the solution testing and validation steps, with particular reference to the system tuning for various operational environments where the applications will run when commercially distributed. This will facilitate the proposition of innovative 5G-enabled applications reducing the overall time-to-market and increasing the competitiveness of SMEs, which will not need huge investments in dedicated 5G infrastructures and specialised testbeds.

During the design phase, an application developer can use the 5G-IANA platform to simplify the design of complex virtual applications or services exploiting 5G network capabilities. For example, he/she can select existing multi-vendor AF/NF from the 5G-IANA portfolio and graphically chain them together with new application components developed to address the requirements of the automotive sectors. Moreover, the application developers could have the possibility to use some nApp examples, called “nApps starter kit”, as a starting point to simplify and speed-up the design and development

of their own applications that can be deployed and integrated in the 5G infrastructure and interact with other applications or network services (e.g., using MEC services for localization or network information, etc.), to build more complex solutions.

The purpose of the "Starter-kit" concept is to make it easier for an application developer to create automotive vertical services, which can be automatically deployed and configured on top of 5G-enabled environments, fully exploiting the capabilities of mobile connectivity. The deployment of specific automotive services, in the form of virtualized AFs/NFs, may exploit the 5G-IANA platform and its orchestration functionalities in order to make use of extreme edge, edge, and cloud resources available in the 5G infrastructures, which includes also the possibility of orchestrating and running applications on top of OBUs and RSUs.

Moreover, the nApp developer may need a 5G-compliant environment for testing the nApps with the possibility to deploy and experimentally validate them in a realistic and configurable environment featuring OBU/RSU and edge computing resources. These resources, together with a flexible 5G infrastructure, are not easily accessible to SMEs and for those reasons, they might benefit from the employment of a ready-to-use platform that provides all the necessary components and extensive monitoring capabilities to better evaluate the behaviour of the applications in a variety of contexts before their roll-out in commercial environments. In particular, the testing phase will benefit from the use of the platform as it will be possible to measure, collect and evaluate network KPIs, a feature that is not available in commercial or public networks.

2.2.8. Application, network function and network application providers (nApp providers)

nApp providers can exploit the 5G-IANA platform as an additional opportunity to provide their nApps to a wide audience of actors. This possibility can enlarge their market, making them also reach SMEs or minor actors that may have trouble in establishing commercial relationships with large nApp providers.

Another benefit, that nApp providers can have, is to test their nApps in an automotive-specific platform. These could help them to identify the strengths and drawbacks of their nApps in this specific context improving in the future the selection of provisioned nApps.

Additionally, they may determine which categories of applications are more popular using their usage information. This information can make it easier for

the providers to decide which nApps to look for in order to better customize their application portfolio to the automotive environment for future provisioning.

2.2.9. Service Creator

Service creators can benefit from the use of the 5G-IANA platform in multiple aspects related to development, implementation, integration, testing and provisioning of resources for their new or existing applications. The 5G-IANA platform offers SMEs the possibility of boosting and accelerating their business models. It permits service creators to be more efficient in the process of creating and then commercializing innovative applications, designed to take advantage of the benefits provided by 5G networks in the automotive sector, among others.

The use of the platform entails a series of advantages for this type of companies:

- One of the main incentives is the lower development time needed. This is because developers can make use of specific existing VNFs or even complete network applications for their own purposes or functional improvements.
- Moreover, there is no need to acquire or use specific hardware resources in the network, since the platform offers HW resources for computing and hosting applications. This reduces the acquisition and maintenance costs of this type of equipment.
- The 5G-IANA platform automatically provides the ability to orchestrate different applications and deploy the resources needed for them.
- It also entails the complete availability of a real test bench that can be used immediately, without the need to create a new one.
- It eases the obtention of network KPIs and the operation of applications. Naturally, this speeds up the maintenance and improvement of the services created.

2.2.10. Service Provider

Service providers are driven to invest in the 5G evolution by the increasing demand for greater bandwidths, ever-faster speeds and near-zero downtime. However, they require robust testing protocols and assurance of increasingly complex 5G architectures to deliver optimal network performance and service quality.

Overall, 5G-IANA provides a set of VNFs, tools and predefined nApps to ease the design and creation of application and services on top of existing

Automotive services for new entrants. The potential incentives and benefits for service providers to use the 5G-IANA platform are:

- Opportunity for cost-less early prototyping and experimentation of new 5G features and use cases utilizing the nApp components, from 5G-IANA repository, labelled per domain availability and service type.
- Ability to understand faster the inherent challenges involved in deploying a new 5G service and how to overcome them, without the user starting the development from scratch.
- Access to a heterogeneous set of already existing virtualized management, communication and optimization functions for the Automotive industry and correlated business areas.
- Abstraction of complexity for nApp chaining by exposing to the user only the high-level information needed for building a comprehensive end-to-end service, hiding the network complexity in the background.
- Ability to deploy an end-to-end network services across different domains due to the virtualization offered and by proposing baseline functionalities to experimenters packaged in starter-kits, divided per type of service.
- Reduction in service creation time utilizing the ready-to-use building blocks from 5G-IANA nApp toolkit and the easily customizable nApp starter kits.
- Intuitive end-to-end service design and chaining to construct nApps with 5G-IANA's graphical nApp composer.
- Access to preconfigured distinct network slices for low latency (uRLLC) and higher data rates (eMBB), holding resources both from the Radio Access and the Core Network, to support a variety of different use case requirements.
- Ability to allocate network resources with the Network Slicing application to fulfil the requirements of a specific service. The QoS needed for a specific service is guaranteed by isolating the allocated resources from other network slices.
- Secured and trusted service provisioning for the Automotive 5G-PPP vertical, with virtualized infrastructure composed of 4 MANO platforms (OBU, RSU, Edge and Cloud Resources).
- Simplified management and orchestration of collections of AI/ML service components, functionalities provided from the DML framework.
- Ability to predict and manage QoS to provide low latency connectivity for mission critical scenarios, using the DMLO.

2.3. 5G-IANA reference model

The 5G-IANA reference model presents the relationships between the different roles in the ecosystem around the AOEP and is presented with all the details in Figure 2.

Figure 2: 5G-IANA reference model

In the reference model, the arrows indicate the relation among the different roles while the direction of the arrow represents the direction of the service flow. The flow of the revenue is on the opposite direction of the arrow, although in some cases there is revenue sharing agreement (in that case there are bidirectional flows and arrows). The rectangular boxes with solid line represent roles, while the ones with dotted lines grouping of roles. We have to note that there are also other relationships between the roles (for example HW vendors provide equipment to all other members of the ecosystem) but these relationships are not examined since they are not affecting the business model of the AOEP.

The business relationships in the reference model are the following:

- **HW equipment:** it represents the relationship between actors for the provisioning of ICT related equipment. It is provided by the HW vendor to the infrastructure providers and the 5G-IANA platform.
- **SW:** it represents the provision of SW by the SW provider to the HW vendor, the infrastructure providers and the 5G-IANA platform.

- **ICT Resources:** it is a general term that includes all kind of resources (connectivity, computational resources, RSU, etc) that are provided by the infrastructure providers. This is a relation among the MNO, the Cloud Infrastructure Provider and the Road Infrastructure provider and the 5G-IANA platform.
- **Resources (vehicles):** it includes the vehicles that are provided by the vehicle manufacturer to the 5G-IANA platform.
- **nApps:** these are the nApps developed by the nApp developers and are tested in the 5G-IANA platform.
- **5G Services:** it represents the provision of 5G services that are ready to be consumed by the end users. These are provided by the service creator to the service provider that is the one that interacts with end users. It can also be provided by the service creator to the 5G-IANA platform in case that it is a service that can be used by other services.
- **AOEP Services:** it describes the portfolio of services that are provided by the 5G-IANA platform, it includes the use of the platform for experimentation, consulting and training services.

The developed 5G-IANA reference model that was presented in this report will be used in the upcoming deliverable D6.2: “Business models for 5G-enabled Automotive service provisioning”. For the scenarios for service provisioning that will be developed, the reference model will be used to describe and analyse the interactions among the different roles within the 5G-IANA ecosystem.

3. BUSINESS MODELS FOR PLATFORMS USED FOR EXPERIMENTATION

To identify the most appropriate business model that can ensure the sustainability of the 5G-IANA platform, useful insights and lessons can be derived from past projects that offered experimentation platforms to third parties.

Probably the most well-known similar projects were the ones funded under the FIRE+ (Future Internet Research & Experimentation) call (ICT-11-2014) [10]. Under this call four projects were funded:

- FIESTA: Federated Interoperable Semantic IoT/cloud Testbeds and Applications [11]
- WiSHFUL: Wireless Software and Hardware platforms for Flexible and Unified radio and network control [12]
- MONROE: Measuring Mobile Broadband Networks in Europe [13]
- RAWFIE: Road-, Air- and Water-based Future Internet Experimentation below [14]
- OrganiCity: OrganiCity - Co-creating smart cities of the future [15]

These projects started in 2015 and were completed in 2018. While the thematic areas they covered were different, all of them performed experimentation in a platform.

The next call that was specific for experimentation was the Future Internet Experimentation - Building a European experimental Infrastructure (ICT-13-2016) [17], under this call the following projects were funded:

- Fed4FIREplus: Federation for FIRE Plus [18]
- FLAME: Facility for Large-scale Adaptive Media Experimentation [19]
- ORCA: Orchestration and Reconfiguration Control Architecture [20]
- 5GINFIRE: Evolving FIRE into a 5G-Oriented Experimental Playground for Vertical industries [21]
- HUB4NGI A Collaborative Platform to Unlock the Value of Next Generation Internet Experimentation (this was a Coordination and Support Action)

These projects were implemented from 2018 to 2022.

In the next sections, a short overview of each of the projects that have examined aspects related to sustainability and business models is presented. The main objective is to present the work that was performed regarding the business models and the sustainability of the platforms (based on information

retrieved from the public deliverables of the projects). That way we can identify success stories and lessons learned that can be used as examples for drafting the business plan and sustainability of 5G-IANA platform.

For WiSHFUL, RAWFIE, ORCA, 5GINFIRE and HUB4NGI there are no public deliverables that are related either to business models or sustainability aspects.

3.1. FIESTA: Federated Interoperable Semantic IoT/cloud Testbeds and Applications

The FIESTA-IoT infrastructure enables experimenters to use a single EaaS API (i.e. the FIESTA-IoT EaaS API) for executing experiments over multiple IoT federated testbeds in a testbed agnostic way i.e. like accessing a single large scale virtualized testbed. FIESTA Project empowers Experimentation-as-a-Service (EaaS) paradigm for sharing and reusing data [16].

Regarding the proposed business model, there is a dedicated deliverable D7.9: “Sustainability and Business Plan V2” that provides the second and final iteration of the sustainability and business plan that were developed for the project. The deliverable presents the value proposition of FIESTA and the business model canvas that was developed using the Experimentation as a Service (EaaS) model. The financial implications of sustaining the FIESTA-IoT platform have been identified along with several charging mechanisms as for example the pay-as-you-go based on data usage for charging; also a subscription-based model and a hybrid model are proposed.

The deliverable also provides information on how the developed platform for experimentation will be exploited and sustained both in the short and long term. Useful feedback was collected during the experimentation phase in which the need to continue the offering of the platform along with the tools and services was identified.

Regarding the target stakeholders, these have been identified as SMEs and the main offerings of the FIESTA are the tools and services provides to the SMEs, EaaS (Experiment as a Service) and DaaS (Data as a Service) stakeholders.

Regarding the operator of the testbed, issues that have been identified are related to the operation and privacy. Regarding operation, the availability of the platform, its maintenance and support must be clear and possibly a Service Level Agreement (SLA) might needed to cover all these aspects. Regarding privacy, the solution proposed includes a bilateral agreement in which the Operators of the platform will state that they will not access the data used during the experiments.

For the long-term sustainability of the platform two type of stakeholders are identified as potential customers: researchers and experimenters along with dataset and data providers.

Regarding exploitation, part of the infrastructure was publicly funded and cannot be exploited commercially, while the costs should only cover direct costs for personnel and additional virtual resources. On the positive side, the use of this type of infrastructure can reduce the costs of sustaining the platform.

The main costs for sustaining the platform are for providing support for the developed services, for personnel mainly system administrators, software developers and marketing and sales.

For pricing, the following models are proposed:

- **Pay-per use** in which the charging is made based on the amount of data that are used during the experimentation.
- **Subscription based** in which the user is charged on a monthly basis. A tiered model is proposed for the subscription - based model providing more benefits to the higher charged packages (standard, executive and premium). A freemium model is also considered for some basic only services.
- **The Red Hat model** is also proposed as candidate in which a fee will be required for covering the costs of highly qualified technical personnel (charged by man hours).

Regarding additional revenue sources these may come from different sources such as donations.

For the short-term sustainability, a plan that is implemented in two phases is proposed, in the first phase (six months after the end of the project) partners involved in the joint plan will continue to support their components at no cost and on a best-can-do basis. During this phase, an investigation about possible investors (such as venture capitals) will take place. In the second phase that will take place until two years after the end of the project, a compensation is foreseen that will be covered by the anticipated revenues. During this period and the lessons learned, representatives from participating partners will form the long-term plan for FIESTA-IoT assets.

3.2. MONROE: Measuring Mobile Broadband Networks in Europe

MONROE proposes to design, build and operate an open, European-scale, and flexible platform with multi-homing capabilities to run experiments on operational 3G/4G Mobile Broadband networks.

For MONROE there is only one deliverable related to business models, where also a draft sustainability model is presented, D7.3: “Exploitation and Sustainability”.

The most important assets are the open access platform, the open-source software that was developed and the open data that were produced during the project.

The different members of the MONROE consortium have exploited the platform in different activities. Academic partners have used MONROE to train Master and PhD students and to establish new collaborations with other institutes. Another activity that was implemented as part of the collaboration was the exchange of personnel among academic institutions. In addition, MONROE has been used as an educational tool for the different classes that the universities provide. Academic partners intend to sustain and extend the platform for future technologies and exploit it in future R&D programs.

Industrial partners had the opportunity to experiment in a real-world testbed and also get access to results of experiments that are of high importance for their future plans. For example, network operators plan to utilize these results to achieve higher network efficiency and reliability and provide increased user experience.

In addition, the consortium of MONROE used the platform to collaborate with other European and National R&D projects.

Regarding the sustainability of the platform, a Framework Agreement has been drafted that defines the relationship between partners. In more detail, it provides all the details regarding management aspects, the distribution of direct costs, and in-kind contribution of partners such as personnel or other resources that are necessary for future maintenance and developing activities. The developed business model provides two options for external users: a subscription model as well as a partnership with the MONROE alliance. The subscription model has two tiers (regular and gold) with gold users having priority over the regular ones by paying a significant higher annual fee. Partners will also pay a fee (equal to the gold users' subscription), they will also contribute to further development, they can provide hardware and software extensions while they participate in upcoming decisions. The alliance

will meet at least once a year to evaluate the platform, the finances and policies.

3.3. OrganiCity – Co-creating smart cities of the future

Built on and extending the FIRE legacy, OrganiCity aimed to build a strong foundation for future sustainable cities through co-creation by a wide range of stakeholders. OrganiCity provides a service for experimentation, which explores how citizens, businesses and city authorities can work together to create digital solutions to urban challenges.

Although the objective is not related to the activities of 5G-IANA, there is an analysis for different models that experimentation platforms can use and how these are related to the project. This information is presented in Deliverable D6.2: “OrganiCity sustainability plan & activity report”.

As part of their activities, they also examined different sustainable models and their relation to the objectives of the project. The examined models are the following:

- **Supply – oriented model:** in which the organizations that are responsible for providing the data are responsible for paying all the platform costs. A subscription model is foreseen for collecting revenues while also there is the possibility of getting revenues for hosting applications by third parties in the developed app store.
- **Freemium model:** the basic service is given for free while a fee can be paid for advanced features or functionalities. The freemium accounts can have limitations on the size of the data they can upload, while paid plans provide more storage, the ability to synchronize their data along with support.
- **Open-source model:** in that case all tools and data will remain for free after the end of the project, the costs are covered from past funding or cross-subsidization from different funding sources. In addition, donations and contributions can also be parts of the funding mechanism.
- **Infrastructure model:** the users pay for access to the platform and its resources that allows them to conduct their experiments and data analysis activities. Different subscription models can be provided with different resources allocated to them.
- **Free with branded advertisement:** in this case the costs are covered by selling advertising space in the platform.

- **Data-oriented model:** revenues come from users that want to access the collected data. Also, in this case different subscription models can be used.
- **Data marketplaces:** these are online stores in which stakeholders can sell and buy data. Suppliers paying a fee can upload their data in the marketplace while consumers can access the data paying a fee. Platform can get revenues by applying a transaction fee while also a freemium model can also be applied in this case.

In the same deliverable, the main cost centres are identified and are related to equipment, maintenance of the platform and services, support, legal and administration and marketing activities.

3.4. Fed4FIREplus: Federation for FIRE Plus

Fed4FIRE+ was based on the legacy of the Fed4FIRE top Internet and network-related experimentation federation and has enhanced the largest federation worldwide of Next Generation Internet (NGI) testbeds, providing open, accessible and reliable facilities to a wide variety of different research and innovation communities and initiatives in Europe.

There were two iterations of the deliverable “Sustainable Governance of the Federation” (2.03 and 2.08) [22] that provide information about the foreseen governance model and how the federation can be sustained.

The Fed4FIRE+ consortium has identified two major stakeholders that need to be sustained: the Federation Core, and the Testbeds. The Federation provides added value to the testbeds that want to become part of it, the testbeds can exist without their participation in the federation. In the rest of the deliverable, we present information mostly about the analysis regarding the testbeds as these are more related to the scope of 5G-IANA platform along with lessons learned regarding the federation that can also be applied to 5G-IANA. The core and the testbeds have different sustainability models, but these are also interdependent as the integrated offering has more value than the individual ones. What is common is that a critical mass of experimenters is required in both cases. To achieve this critical mass of experimenters, it is crucial that the offering of the platform is relevant to the needs of the community that it targets. Another useful observation is that there are no repeated or long-term users, they usually come once so there is an increased need to increase the targeted market and attract new experimenters.

For the testbeds, the main customers were SMEs and most of them were geographically located in South Europe. Another benefit that the testbeds

have is that they can act as innovation hubs for the local communities that these are located. During the open calls they provided access for experimenters without any charge, but this model is highly unlikely to be used after the end of the project where no fund will be available.

As also observed in FIESTA, the need to have clear policies and compliance to the different regulations is also important; here GDPR is also mentioned (it was not a law during the time FIESTA was running).

Regarding funding, not only the possible sources must be identified but also a strategy on how each of them can be approached and how a funding without interruption may happen, possibly combining different sources of funding. Diversification of funding is common practice; by securing funding from different sources, platforms can be sustained even if one of the funding sources is no more available. That way the risk of having periods without funding will be minimized.

The possible payment methods include annual fee for accessing the testbed, on a pay-as-you-go model. A freemium model for academic partners is also suggested on a best effort basis or/and providing in-kind contribution such as resources, datasets and testimonials as a word-of-mouth advertisement. For small SMEs, a fee is foreseen that can vary depending on factors such as the complexity of the experiment and/or the duration, bigger companies can also provide in-kind contribution such as equipment, software tools licences etc.

The value of the platform is high especially for SMEs that have no access to experimentation platforms in a cost-effective way.

To achieve the objective of identifying funding sources and drafting the appropriate strategy a specific instrument is proposed to be formed. Sources of funding can be either national funding programmes, Public Private Partnerships (PPP), European grants or R&D programmes, and revenues coming from experimenters. One of the remarks of Fed4FIRE+ based also in experiences from past projects is that commercial funding for testbeds is extremely rare.

Another critical point is that even if funding is found, this will most likely cover only the expenses of maintaining the testbed and thus cannot provide grants to experimenters (that was the case during the open calls of the project).

Another instrument that is proposed is the one that undertakes the operation and the maintenance of the platform and also the role of defining the contribution of the different parties that are part of the initiative. Different instruments are also foreseen that can take the roles of service provider and marketing activities.

As different parties participate in the project, it is also of high importance to define what parts need to be sustained.

3.5. FLAME Facility for Large-scale Adaptive Media Experimentation

The project's main objective is to establish a trusted platform that brings together technology, creative sectors, and consumers to pioneer innovative media applications and services. Through real-life experimentation and advanced tools, FLAME will empower industry players, SMEs, and entrepreneurs to gain valuable insights into solution performance, acceptance and viability. There are 4 sites in Italy, Spain and UK with different design and hardware in which the replicas of FLAME have been deployed allowing the successful execution of use cases. The targeted stakeholders were from the Media vertical and the use cases were targeted around smart cities. There are two deliverables [23] examining the aspects of sustainability of the infrastructure that were deployed in smart cities, in D2.2: "Sustainability and Governance Models for Experimental Infrastructures", the case of "Bristol Is Open" (BiO) is examined while in D2.5: "Sustainability and Governance Models for Platforms and Infrastructures v6", information about the four deployed testbeds is provided.

One of the main outcomes is that there is no definitive EaaS business model applicable to European Smart Cities that can be adopted to the FLAME platform due to ecosystem variations between existing smart cities. Based on this fact, the different approaches used by each of the cities are presented.

Bristol Is Open is a smart city research and development platform which combines multiple experimental facilities and capabilities within a city operating system, that enables to offer City Experimentation as a Service, with open, flexible and programmable functionalities for partners seeking to test smart city technology within a physical world setting.

The platform is a joint venture between University of Bristol (UoB) and Bristol City Council (BCC). BiO has also interactions with corporate partners and local SMEs for the operation of the infrastructure and the provision of new hardware deployed in the testbed. The revenues are coming from experimentation of the commercial partners that want to use the testbed for experimentation with innovative hardware and the implementation of smart cities use cases.

There are three types of agreements offered to these stakeholders, some of them are based on PPP model:

- **Partnership:** that allows partners to run their experiments for a duration of three years.

- **Collaboration:** that allows collaborators to provide hardware and software as in-kind contribution and showcase on the testbed without any fees.
- **Experimentation:** experimenters are allowed to use certain parts of the infrastructure for free, but the experimentation kit remains in BiO.

Other sources of funding include the participation in R&D projects at national and European level.

For the developed testbed in Barcelona, the plan is to use it for experimentation in new R&D projects generating revenues indirectly. The main reason behind this approach is that one of the partners (i2CAT) is a non-profit entity and thus cannot generate revenues from experimentation.

The testbed in Sicily revenues can come from offering the testbed to rural communities for free but as a bundle of other services. Another option is to use with an Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) or Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) model where third parties can use the testbed resources.

The same models IaaS and PaaS are also proposed for the London testbed, that was initially developed from the UK government and has been used as a support tool to different R&D projects. The generated revenues will be used to cover the running costs of the testbed.

3.6. 5G-IANA business model

Although the presented business models are not directly comparable, as the platforms have different scope, they provide valuable information about the possible options that can be adopted by the 5G-IANA platform in order to increase its sustainability. Some of the most important findings are the following:

- It is important to analyse all the costs associated with the sustainability of the platform. This analysis is part of the activities of WP6, while the detailed report regarding the foreseen costs along with the creation of a business plan will be reported in D6.4: Techno-economic analysis and sustainability of 5G- IANA business models, as was initially planned. The participation of each partner must be considered, and it can include in-kind contribution such as resources or personnel.
- Receiving feedback from experimenters during the Open Calls provides valuable information. In 5G-IANA, we have identified that receiving feedback is important, and thus, we conducted a survey before the Open Calls, to understand third party expectations (presented in the

- next chapter). In addition, there is a reporting period at the end of each Open Call that we will receive feedback from the experimenters.
- Regarding funding, in almost all of the cases the funding comes from the actual users of the platform by different models such as per use, subscription based for accessing the platform, and fees for training and consulting services. Different tiers for subscription are also foreseen. A mix of funding coming from different sources can also be utilised.
 - For the exploitation, not in all cases the whole platform was sustained after the end of the project. The decision depended on the individual partners' interests. In almost all cases, part of the platform was reused either in new research projects or other parts were exploited individually by their respective owners.
 - There is no unique business model that was followed by all the platforms; each was adapted based on the nature of the platform, the interests of the partners and the foreseen demand by third parties.

Based on the lessons learned from the previous projects, the business model for the 5G-IANA platform will be developed. In this first deliverable, the initial version will be presented based on the discussions until now among the different partners of the 5G-IANA consortium. An updated version of the business model with more details will be presented in D6.2: "Business models for 5G-enabled Automotive service provisioning".

The problems that the 5G-IANA AOEP aims to address are associated with the lack of specialised 5G experimental platforms that can be accessible by third party experimenters. In addition, there are no testbeds available that offer access to resources specific to the automotive vertical, while the VNF repository and the nApp toolkit can assist third parties to compose their own services even if their level of expertise is low.

Regarding the competition there are some generic emulators that have a number of limitations with the most important to be the lack of resources needed for the development of services in the automotive vertical. There are other experimental platforms from other 5G projects that are developed under the same call, from 5G-PPP earlier phases or from national funded projects; but to the best of our knowledge no platform is targeting explicitly the automotive vertical.

The solution that the 5G-IANA platform offers includes 5G testbeds, HW resources, SW resources and toolkits, along with human capital that are difficult to be offered from other stakeholders, while MNOs that could potentially offer such resources are not for the moment eager to open up their networks to external parties.

The “Business Model Canvas” was developed by Osterwalder and Pigneur [24] and is used to represent the business model in a structured and comprehensive way. It is used as a blueprint to define business strategies for enterprises. The business model canvas can be split into three major groups of building blocks: The right part is the customer group, the left part focuses on resources of a business model while in the bottom the financial structure with revenue streams and costs is represented.

The business model canvas that has been created for the 5G-IANA platform is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Business Canvas for the 5G-IANA platform

The description for each of the elements of the business model canvas:

Key partners

There are several key partners that are providing all the resources that are essential for the operation of the 5G-IANA platform as defined in the reference model. The network operators and other infrastructure operators or owners are providing the necessary ICT resources, which include connectivity, computational and storage resources (that can be either physical or virtual). The HW providers supply all the required HW that is required for the operation of the 5G-IANA platform such as computers, CPUs, GPUs, routers, switches etc. In case that a local private cloud will be built (the other option is getting it as a service from a cloud provider) there will be increased needs for these

types of resources. The SW providers will provide the necessary SW that is essential for the operation of the platform. SMEs and R&D institutions are the partners that will provide the human capital with the expertise to operate the 5G-IANA platform (for example personnel of the partners that are part of the 5G-IANA consortium).

Key activities

The most important activity is the execution of the experiments from third parties that will use the 5G-IANA platform. The term Experimentation as a Service (EaaS) has been introduced from other platforms [25], and other 5GPP projects [26], [27] and will also be used here. The provision of EaaS allows a number of additional complementary activities such as consulting, training and support activities to experimenters that are targeting users of the platform with limited expertise or knowledge. The support service will provide assistance in case that third parties are experiencing technical difficulties with the platform. Training can be provided either for the operation and functionalities of the platform or for the design and execution of experiments. The consulting services can be provided to experimenters at different levels like for example provide insights on how they can create a service (for the ones that lack the expertise and knowledge), to technical assistance on improving their service or even mentoring to help them assess the market opportunities and develop a business plan for their offerings. Services like the improvement of functionality and the evaluation of the KPIs can also be provided or assistance in the development and integration of nApps.

Key Resources

All the parts that constitute the 5G-IANA platform and that will be used for the experimentation are considered key resources (HW, SW, testbeds, OBUs, MEC etc.) The expertise of the human capital is also another of the key resources since it can provide their knowledge to third parties that want to take advantage of the platform. The repository of VNFs is also an important resource since it can facilitate the creation of new services and reduce the service creation time. Existing datasets (like for example from previous experimenters that want to share them) can facilitate the validation of new services. Finally, the services that can be utilized from other services (like for example the one in UC6) can be considered key resources (there will be some incentives for experimenters that want to share their services).

Value propositions

The main value proposition is the AOEP, that constitutes from a number of elements. The most important are the AF/NF repository, the nApp toolkit, the network management and orchestration, the distributed AI/ML framework, the

virtualised OBU. The platform is offering also the human capital to allow third parties without expertise to develop their own applications.

Customer relationships

Regarding the customer relationships due to the nature of the provided services these must be personalised to the needs of each experimenter using both online and offline methods. The online can be through the website or using teleconference platforms.

Channels

To promote the platform the partners involved in the 5G-IANA platform and their respective networks should be utilised. The participation in events, congresses and fairs in which developers in the automotive industry participate will be used as it can attract an increased number of possible users that would not be possible with the other channels. The creation and presentation of demos and success stories can increase the chances of collaboration. The automotive association and 5G-PPP Working Groups in which experimenters participate is another channel that will be used. Finally, start-ups in the automotive vertical, incubators in each country and innovation clusters can be a promising contact point.

Customer segments

All the parties that have an interest in doing experiments in the 5G-IANA platform, the developers (and providers) of nApps and services that are targeting the automotive vertical. Also, users of services like for example fleet and road operators that want to test their applications or services.

Cost Structure

It includes the cost associated with the required resources of running the 5G-IANA platform. Personnel cost for type of employees like technical experts, those providing support, marketing and brand and other auxiliary roles like account department, legal, etc: these can be outsourced in the beginning and if the needs increase to become permanent staff. The costs of the infrastructure include the necessary HW and SW licences, cost for initial installation, further development of the platform and system integration.

Revenue streams

There are different options regarding the revenue streams depending on the type of services that will be offered after the end of the project. In case that the platform will remain open to third parties funding must be found from innovation and public funds at national or EU level. Since the sustainability of the platform depend on the funding another option would be to offer some of basic functionalities as free but with limited capabilities and support. A subscription-based model can be used providing access to a predefined

packet of resources and support. In case some of the experimenters want to use some extra resources, the charging can be made based on the number and type of resources are used, the duration of the experiment, the level of required support and consulting. A revenue sharing agreement can be made with experimenters that want to share their applications or services or their data to other users in the platform. That could be beneficial for all involved parties and increase the impact of the 5G-IANA platform.

4.5G-IANA SURVEY REGARDING THIRD PARTY EXPECTATIONS

The need to collect information about the expectations from the 5G-IANA platform is important, in the view of preparing an open platform that is targeted to SMEs for exploitation. Therefore, a focused survey has been prepared, with the objective to collect such feedback. The outcome of this survey will help the consortium to better understand the needs of experimenters and allocate the resources to cover their needs. For each of the questions, the potential exploitation of the received feedback is presented.

The aim of this section is to analyse the expectations of potential third-party experimenters from the 5G-IANA AOEP. To collect the required input a questionnaire was created, and an online survey was designed. The survey was promoted through the project website and 5G-IANA partners and circulated through 5G-PPP and 6G-IA mailing lists (dissemination and communication leaders, working groups, technical board, verticals, associate members and members of the 6G-IA, SME working group) to SMEs that are working on the development and provisioning of nApps in the automotive vertical. It was also distributed to the other ICT-41 projects, to ERTICO partners, to our External Advisory Board, and to SMEs that were identified as possible users of the 5G-IANA platform. The complete list of the questions is presented in Annex I and is structured as follows:

- Introductory page with information about the survey.
- Profiling questions of the participants.
- Sections for comparison and classification of the different aspects of the platform using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) methodology such as the different technologies used in the platform, the offered resources and the support options.
- Questions regarding the most important use cases, the expectations of third parties for resources, the most important KPIs that should be monitored, the open data, and the participants' intentions to take part in the experimentation phase.

The following sections present the analysis of the collected responses for the different questions.

4.1. Online survey

The survey was conducted online and was created using an open-source tool (LimeSurvey). No personal information was collected from the responders (except, optionally, for the e-mails in case they wanted to be informed for upcoming activities). The link of the survey was shared among the 5G-IANA partners with the note to further communicate it to potential third parties that would like to experiment in the AOEP. Furthermore, it was disseminated through the 5G-PPP mailing lists with an introductory e-mail explaining the purpose of the survey. It remained open for three weeks and in total 23 participants have completed all the requested questions.

4.2. Profile of participants

Regarding the participants' profile (Figure 4) most of them were SMEs (20), two come from industry and one from academia and research institutions.

Figure 4: Profile

Regarding their field of expertise most of the responders responded that they are developing applications followed by researchers (the sum of numbers as presented in Figure 5 exceeds 100% as in this question more than one selection was permitted).

Figure 5: Field of expertise

The next question was about the participants' involvement in the automotive sector either by offering a service or a platform, a HW device or an application. The results (presented in Figure 6) reveal that almost half of them (10) have no such product or service in the automotive vertical (yet). Out of the rest of the 13 responders, most of them have software or an application (10), a platform or a service (7) and 4 of them have a HW device. In this question more than one choice can be selected, thus, the total percentage sums up over 100%.

Figure 6: Involvement in automotive industry

The next question requested their familiarity with the 5G ecosystem and the creation of nApps.

The results presented in Figure 7 reveal that 61% has developed or are developing a nApp (with 17.4% to have developed more than one). An equal percentage has not yet developed any nApp but they are considering to do it, and 13% are familiar with the term as part of their research activities. Only 8.67% (2 responders) are not familiar with the term and do not plan to do any development.

Figure 7: Familiarity with 5G ecosystem

4.3. Prioritization of platform general features

AHP is a technique for assisting taking complex decisions. It is based on a comprehensive framework that decomposes unstructured complex problems into a multi-level hierarchy that is composed of interrelated criteria and decision alternatives. Introducing the judgments of experts on both qualitative and quantitative criteria, AHP achieves to quantify the preferences of the experts. By combining all the different judgments, it provides priorities among the criteria and the alternatives.

The AHP method was developed by Thomas Saaty [28] and initially it was used for military applications. The last decades it has been applied in different sectors such as engineering [29], industry [30] and manufacturing [31]. More information about the method and how has been used as a tool to rank alternative options in the ICT domain can be found in [32],[33].

Several steps are required to reach the final result as illustrated in Figure 8. The first step is about the formulation of the problem, and it includes the determination of the criteria and sub-criteria that are necessary for the achievement of the final objective. These are defined by organizing workshops and interviews with the experts in which the various elements are discussed. The multi-level hierarchy is then formulated, the primary level is the objective that must be achieved followed by the criteria in the next level. Finally, in the lower level there are sub-criteria (for each criterion) that are used to better present specific features that each criterion has.

Figure 8: Steps for analytic hierarchy process

When the criteria and sub-criteria are determined, the hierarchical structure is completed and the questionnaires that must be answered by experts can be created (step 2). The questionnaires are created asking for pairwise comparisons from the experts among the same levels of the hierarchy. The comparisons are performed using the nine levels that are presented in Table 1. The last step included the calculation of weights for criteria and sub-criteria.

Table 1: The Saaty Rating Scale

Intensity of	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	The two criteria have equally contribution
3	Moderate importance	Experience and judgment favor one of the criteria
5	Strong importance	The criterion is strongly favored
7	Very strong importance	The criterion is dominant
9	Extreme importance	The criterion is favored by at least an order of magnitude
2, 4, 6, 8	Intermediate values	Intermediate values that used as alternatives between two of the above numbers

The survey was designed by conducting workshops with partners organized by WP6 and the following set of criteria were identified:

- Technology
- Resources
- Support

Each of the above criteria was further analysed into sub-criteria, which are attributes that are closely related to the criteria. For the technology the following sub-criteria were identified:

- **Application Orchestration:** the entry point for service providers. It exposes functionalities for designing distributed services composed by nApps. This layer hosts also a catalogue of available nApps that can be used and chained to realize the desired service.

- **Network Orchestration Platform:** this layer implements the functionalities for verifying the availability of a network slice instance suitable for supporting the operation of the vertical service. It also handles the orchestration of computational resources to be allocated to run the nApps.
- **Distributed AI/ML Framework:** provides explicit support for ML-oriented services, including FL primitives.
- **Evaluation and KPI testing:** it realises the collection of data from distributed data sources (i.e., Network Application, infrastructure hosts etc.) and provides analytics based on service-level policies to optimize the Lifecycle Management (LCM) operations.

For the resources the following type has been identified as the most important:

- HW resources (OBUs)
- Virtualised Application Functions / Network Functions (AFs/NFs)
- HW resources (MEC)

Finally, for the support the most important aspects have been identified:

- Support by email / on-line form
- Ticketing System
- Webinars / Videos (interactive)
- Training by experts

The pair wise comparisons were introduced in the survey, an example is illustrated in Figure 9. After the completion of the survey the responses were imported in MATLAB in order to estimate the priorities of the sub-criteria.

Which of the following do you consider more important?

Comparison 1: H/W resources (OBUs) vs. Virtualised Application Functions / Network Functions

Comparison 2: H/W resources (OBUs) vs. H/W resources (MEC)

Comparison 3: Virtualised Application Functions / Network Functions vs. H/W resources (MEC)

Figure 9: Example question

Figure 10: Prioritization of technology sub-criteria

The results for the technology sub-criteria are presented in Figure 10. According to the opinion of the experts the most important technology used in the AOEP is the Application orchestration with a weight of 35%. Evaluation and KPI testing, and the Network orchestration platform are following with weights of 25% and 24% respectively, while the distributed AI/ML framework has a weight of 16%. The application orchestration is highly valued among the experts as it can facilitate the deployment of new services and reduce the service creation time.

Figure 11: Prioritization of resources sub-criteria

Regarding the sub-criteria related to the offered resources the opinion of the experts are divided almost equally (Figure 11). The Virtualized AFs/NFs have a slightly higher weight of 40% compared to the two different types of resources (MEC and OBUs) that both have a weight equal to 30%. There is no distinct

difference among the valuation of the different resources; experts seem to consider them of almost equal value for running their experiments.

Figure 12: Prioritization of support sub-criteria

For the different options for support (Figure 12), the training by experts has a weight of 41%. Two other options have similar scores: ticketing system (26%) and webinars and videos (24%), while the support with methods such as email and an online form have the lower weight equal with 10%.

Experts have the opinion that the human capital of the 5G-IANA platform is one of the most important assets and thus want to benefit as much as they can from it. They also prefer the interactive ways of communicating instead of traditional communication using e-mails and online forms.

4.4. Technical expectations from the 5G-IANA platform

The first question that we raised to the participants of the survey required their feedback about the most important use case categories for the automotive sector. The participants could choose between the following categories:

- Hazard notification, such as high-risk driving detection (5G-IANA UC5 and UC7 belong to this broad category);
- Vehicle movement, such as remote driving (5G-IANA UC1 and UC2 belong to this broad category);
- Infotainment purposes, such as in-vehicle AR/VR applications (5G-IANA UC3 and UC4 belong to this category);
- A vertical-agnostic category, acting as an “umbrella” to any use case, which concerns for instance network status monitoring for predictive QoS (5G-IANA UC6 belongs to this category).

Figure 13: Importance of different UC categories

The results (Figure 13) reveal a rough prioritization of the interest of the automotive use cases, as well as, indirectly, of the project’s own use cases: 1. Hazard-notification, 2. Infotainment, 3. Vehicle movement, 4. Vertical-agnostic. We believe that the industry is not yet well-familiarised with vertical-agnostic use cases though; thus, the provided feedback. The project will therefore contribute towards emphasizing the potential benefits for OEMs from AOEP-enabled network status monitoring, by showcasing the UC6 in parallel with other use cases (related to vehicle movement, infotainment, etc.). The detailed results for each of these graphs are presented in Appendix II.

Exploitation: The feedback from this question helps the project identify the expected public interest and potential impression from the respective to-be-organised demos towards the end of the project. Overall, this can be valuable input for 5G-IANA while a) promoting the AOEP platform capabilities (to give emphasis on specific supported use cases) to potentially attract more third-party experimenters, b) organising and advertising the demo activities, to attract industrial interest, c) preparing AFs/NFs with the mindset that hazard-notification- and infotainment-related ones may be the ones of most interest and reusability potential by third parties.

Figure 14: Importance of HW resources

The next question that we raised to the participants of the survey concerned the importance of HW-related resources for potentially running their experiments on the AOEP platform. The third parties seem to require central processing the most, followed by the need for RAM, and storage/graphics processing. Some of the experiments might not need GPUs at all, which provides us an insight about such types of experiments, while others consider the use of GPU extremely important.

Exploitation: Since we did not require specific values for RAM/CPU/etc. at this early stage (such a request might discourage some of the participants and potentially lead them to abandon the survey), we mainly used it to get a rough idea about what kind of experiments the 5G-IANA should be able to support in terms of resource requirements. We conclude that in order to support the broader possible spectrum of experimenters, we should pay attention equally to all factors and make sure that the platform can support central/graphics-processing-hungry applications, as well as memory/storage-hungry ones, as we would not like to exclude any potential experimenters due to the platform's HW resources insufficiency.

Figure 15: Expectations for maximum Round-Trip Time

Figure 16: Expectations for minimum UL user rate

Figure 17: Expectations for minimum DL user rate

Figure 18: Expectations for minimum Reliability

The purpose of the previous four-part question is to record the third parties' feedback regarding the "at least" values for specific metrics, so that their applications may run smoothly with 5G support, namely: maximum Round Trip Time (RTT), minimum Upload and Download rate, as well as the minimum reliability required for the application to function properly (the definitions of all these metrics have been provided in the respective survey question – see Appendix).

With the responses of the participants, we have had the opportunity to get numerical values regarding the expectations from the 5G network, and the requirements that it would have to fulfil in the “worst case scenario”. In terms of RTT, we realise that third parties may wish to run either time-insensitive (27%: 50-100ms) or, more often, time-critical applications (73%: 1-50ms). In terms of throughput required, the majority would need a minimum of 10-50Mbps UL, and 100-300Mbps DL. Reliability is very critical, as 95% would need more than 99%.

Exploitation: This feedback will be provided to NOKIA and Telecom Slovenia testbeds, for further processing.

Figure 19: Minimum number of vehicles/OBUs

The purpose of this question (free text question) on the need for any far edge resources will help 5G-IANA understand the various application requirements regarding vehicle and OBU availability. 9.1% of the experiments would not require any vehicles, 59.1% would require 1-3 vehicles, 27.3% would need 4-10 vehicles, and 4.5% declared 1000 vehicles (which cannot be supported by the project though).

Exploitation: This information will be used by the project in order to better prepare for the third-party experimentation activities. However, there is a constraint on the number of available OBUs that the project can support (provided by LINKS and UULM). Since there seems to be a need though for even more vehicles by some parties, the project will consider the possibility of emulated OBUs (virtualised OBUs) as well, integrated into CARLA [34].

The next question required feedback on the anticipated time for the actual execution of an experiment using the 5G-IANA platform. Most of the experimenters (43%) would require more than a week, around 48% between 2-7 days, and the rest approximately 9% for 1 day or less.

Exploitation: This question has provided us with valuable feedback in order to understand a) the timely nature of anticipated experiments, b) the maximum number of third party experimenters that we would be able to support during the project's Open Calls, c) the estimated occupancy of the project's testbeds, and d) the expected time for providing technical support to the experimenters.

Figure 20: Required experimentation time

Figure 21: Open data

The following question required feedback about the usefulness third parties find in the data that will be openly available by the project (with respect to the Data Management Plan). It is observed that the majority of the participants are interested in open Virtual AFs and NFs, which stresses the need for providing reusable functions (and nApps, thereof), that could be further exploited through the project’s use cases. Equally important are application monitoring data, something that emphasizes a) the need for collecting application-related data and b) this also extends to the need for developing a user-friendly GUI “on top of” the platform, to assist the experimenters directly observe the behavior of their applications. Existing datasets seem to have less value for the experimenters, which can be attributed to the participants’ assumption that such datasets would be too use-case specific and thus, not help them in some direction; so, we will try to mitigate this impression when defining datasets in the revised DMP (we already define one such generic dataset related to network status monitoring – UC6). Finally, evaluation data, network monitoring data and local resources monitoring data seem to be of moderate value.

Exploitation: 5G-IANA plans to create open datasets, offer AFs/NFs to the third parties, publish evaluation metrics’ values, and also collect and keep logs of application-, network-, and local resources monitoring-data. This question has helped us verify that the project is indeed in the right direction with what concerns industrial interest for such openly available information, and will help us also when revising the DMP, and when designing the AOEP GUI (as explained above).

Figure 22: Importance of different aspects (onboarding ease, service creation time)

The following question was targeted to understand the third parties’ impression regarding the importance of two very specific aspects of the AOEP:

- The ease of onboarding the virtual applications or nApps on the AOEP;
- The need for low service creation time.

It has been shown that the former is critical for third party experimenters, while the latter is also very important.

Exploitation: The project is already working on (and indeed verifies) that the platform should be as experimenter-friendly as possible, especially with what concerns the onboarding of AFs/NFs/nApps. Except for designing the nApp toolkit, and related components (e.g., graphical nApp composer, nApp Catalogue) in an intuitive way, the project will prepare technical manuals and webinars in order to help the interested parties become easily acquainted with the platform. Besides, in the context of the third party engagement plan (through the project’s Open Calls), the consortium will offer both training (before the actual experimentation) and support (during the actual, live onboarding and validation phase).

Figure 23: Parameters that should be defined through the UI

The following question concerned the importance of specific parameters that would be valuable to be offered through the AOEP GUI. Our goal has been to identify to which parameters the experimenters add value, and we should therefore offer them as manageable capabilities:

- Determining the network location of AF/NF. The third parties would therefore have the freedom to select on which segment they wish these functions to be onboarded (cloud / edge / far-edge).
- Determining the geographical location of targeted OBUs. This would give them the capability to select a subset of available vehicles (and OBUs, thereof) based on any application-specific criteria.
- Determining high level networking KPIs that should be met for a certain AF. This means the experimenters could be given the possibility to define the desired value for network KPIs such as RTT, data rates, etc., and the platform should manage to meet such declared expectations. This option has been considered of utmost importance among the provided options.
- Finally, determining which targeted KPIs to be monitored. This would ease the experimenters to monitor only KPIs of interest, and not be overwhelmed by too much and unnecessary information.

Exploitation: 5G-IANA will take these aspects into consideration while designing the AOEP GUI.

Figure 24: Familiarity with different technical concepts

The following question was targeted to understand the level of familiarisation of the potential third parties with concepts/technologies embraced in 5G-IANA, namely: the FLOWER framework for federated learning, LTE and 5G radio systems, and nApps in general. Based on the participants' feedback, we understand that third parties on average are not so familiar with FLOWER, while around half of them are very familiar with the nApp concept; this is an encouraging result as it implies high interest of third parties to platforms offering nApp capabilities such as 5G-IANA. Finally, the participants are very familiar with 5G (and less with LTE).

Exploitation: Such information provides us insights about the profile of interested third parties and about the expected time and effort of the 5G-IANA human capital for the purposes of third party experimentation (both pre-testing and validation phases – Section 4).

Figure 25: Monitoring of service level KPIs

Figure 26: Monitoring of network level KPIs

The next two questions concerned the feedback from third parties regarding the a) service-level and b) network-level KPIs that they consider as essential to be monitored for the successful experimentation of their application. The definitions of these KPIs were also provided to ensure common understanding (see Appendix I). In order of priority, they are ranked as follows (taking into account the sum of “very” and “extremely” votes):

- E2E reliability (as also recorded in a previous question, a lot of emphasis is put on the reliability factor)
- E2E latency
- Service availability and Quality of Experience (QoE)
- Application jitter
- Service deployment time
- Algorithm prediction accuracy

Regarding network-level KPIs, the respective ranking is as follows:

- RTT
- Reliability
- UL (DL) user data rate
- UL (DL) packet loss rate

Exploitation: 5G-IANA will take this feedback into consideration while a) designing (revising) the validation methodology (within Task 5.1) and b) designing the GUI of the AOEP, so as to put emphasis on the most essential KPIs from an experimenter’s point of view.

Figure 27: Participation in the Open Call

The next question concerned the interest of the participants of the survey in the planned project’s Open Call (the concept of the Open Call was described first – see Appendix). Approximately one third of the participants has replied

positively, and another one third has replied “maybe”. Moreover, participants had the option to provide us with their e-mail address (as the survey was totally anonymous) in case they would like to be informed when the Open Call is announced (we have received 6 e-mail addresses through this process).

Figure 28: Purpose of experimentation

In case the answer to the previous question was “yes” or “maybe”, the final question appeared to the participants, in order to understand the motivation behind their interest to potentially experiment with the AOEP platform. We have received diverse answers to this question (in order of priority): some of the third parties would be interested in testing an application using 5G or in developing a new product, while others would be interested in being involved just for research purposes, or they have an interest in the business model in general or they are interested in developing a new NF/AF/nApp.

For the sake of completeness, we also present below the provided free text regarding “*any other important aspect that was not covered by the survey*”:

- “Interested in the info/entertainment use case on moving vehicles or nApps”
- “We would like to exchange data with vehicles, control them remotely, stream the vehicle cameras”
- “Trusted communication between edge deployed functions and connected far edge nodes (here OBU’s)”.

5. CONCLUSION

This deliverable presented the main roles of the ecosystem that is created around the 5G-IANA platform. The reference diagram provided details about the interactions among the actors. Findings regarding business models adopted by other experimental platforms have been reviewed and the best practices have been identified. Based on this input, the initial business model of the 5G-IANA platform was presented with a detailed explanation of all building blocks of the created business canvas.

The results of the online survey that has as an objective to capture the expectations of third parties from the 5G-IANA platform were presented and commented. One of the most important aspects is that the majority of the participants are interested in open Virtual AFs and NFs, which stresses the need for providing reusable functions.

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APPENDIX I – QUESTIONNAIRE

5G-IANA survey regarding third party expectations

Welcome to the 5G-IANA survey with the objective to collect the expectations from potential third party experimenters regarding the 5G-IANA Automotive Open Experimental Platform (AOEP).

5G-IANA is a H2020 ICT-41 Innovation Action project that aims at providing a 5G AOEP in which third party experimenters in the Automotive-related 5G-PPP vertical will have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services. An example of such services is illustrated in the next figure

AOEP will include a set of hardware and software resources that provide the compute and communication/transport infrastructure as well as the management and orchestration components, coupled with Network Applications (NetApp) Toolkit tailored to the Automotive industry.

The survey is expected to last 15 minutes.

You can learn more about the project on the [website](#) and follow us on the social media:

- Twitter: [@IANA_5G](#)
- LinkedIn: [5G_IANA](#)

5G-IANA project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016427.

This survey is anonymous.

The record of your survey responses does not contain any identifying information about you, unless a specific survey question explicitly asked for it.

If you used an identifying access code to access this survey, please rest assured that this code will not be stored together with your responses. It is managed in a separate database and will only be updated to indicate whether you did (or did not) complete this survey. There is no way of matching identification access codes with survey responses.

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Figure 29: First page of the survey

Profile

***Which of the following better suits your profile?**

Choose one of the following answers

SME

Academia / Research Institute

Industry

Other

***What is your field of expertise?**

Check all that apply

Software House - Application Developer

Vendor

Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM)

Mobile Network Operator (MNO)

Researcher

Other

***Do you have a product or service in the automotive industry? (please specify)**

Check all that apply

Platform or service

Software or Application

Hardware (Device / Vehicle)

No

***Are you familiar with the 5G ecosystem, creation of NetApps?**

A NetApp is a virtual application that can be deployed in a 5G infrastructure and can use 5G services (e.g., connectivity). A NetApp can be composed by one or multiple application and/or network functionalities

- Application Functions (AF) implement the Vertical Service logic
- Network Functions (NF) implement the network/communication functionalities

 Application and network functionalities can be deployed in the form of virtual, cloud-native or physical functions

 An Automotive Vertical Service can be composed by one or multiple NetApps

 NetApps can be designed to solve specific purposes:

- Implement the application logic
- Provide a complementary monitoring service
- Provide a complementary AI-driven optimization service
- Provide the needed communication functionalities Etc.

Choose one of the following answers

No

No but we are considering the creation of NetApps

Yes we have developed (or developing) a NetApp

Yes we have developed more than one NetApps

Theoretically / as a researcher

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Figure 30: Profile section

Comparison of technologies

5G-IANA project has identified the following four technologies as the most important offering of the AOEP.

- **Application Orchestration:** the entry point for service providers. It exposes functionalities for designing distributed services composed by Network Applications. This layer hosts also a catalogue of available Network Applications that can be used and chained to realize the desired service.
- **Network Orchestration Platform:** this layer implements the functionalities for verifying the availability of a network slice instance suitable for supporting the operation of the vertical service. It also handles the orchestration of computational resources to be allocated to run the Network Applications.
- **Distributed AI/ML Framework:** provides explicit support for ML-oriented services, including FL primitives.
- **Evaluation and KPI testing:** it realizes the collection of data from distributed data sources (i.e., Network Application, infrastructure hosts etc.) and provides analytics based on service-level policies to optimize the Lifecycle Management (LCM) operations.

Please answer the questions using the following instructions:

Each criterion will be rated according to its degree of relative importance to the other criteria within the group using pair wise comparisons to rank them. Please indicate your preference between two criteria by providing your preference between 1 and 9.

When two criteria are of equal importance, they should take a score of 1. When one criterion is more important than another criterion, then it should take a score between 2 and 9, depending on how much more important it is compared to the other criterion, with 9 indicating that is much more important.

Please indicate your preference between two criteria by providing your preference between 1 and 9

Number	Scale
9	Extremely preferred
8	Very strong to extremely preferred
7	Very strong preferred
6	Strongly to very strongly preferred
5	Strongly preferred
4	Moderately to strongly preferred
3	Moderately preferred
2	Equally to moderately preferred
1	Equally preferred

Which of the following do you consider more important?

Application orchestration (NetApps toolkit)

Network Orchestration platform

[Reset](#)

Application orchestration (NetApps toolkit)

Distributed AI/ML framework

[Reset](#)

Application orchestration (NetApps toolkit)

Evaluation & KPI testing

[Reset](#)

Network Orchestration platform

Distributed AI/ML framework

[Reset](#)

Network Orchestration platform

Evaluation & KPI testing

[Reset](#)

Distributed AI/ML framework

Evaluation & KPI testing

[Reset](#)

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Figure 31: Comparison of technologies section

Comparison of resources

5G-IANA project has identified the following type of resources as the most important offering of the AOEP:

- H/W resources (OBUs)
- Virtualised Application Functions / Network Functions
- H/W resources (MEC)

Please answer the questions using the following instructions:

Each criterion will be rated according to its degree of relative importance to the other criteria within the group using pair wise comparisons to rank them. Please indicate your preference between two criteria by providing your preference between 1 and 9.

When two criteria are of equal importance, they should take a score of 1. When one criterion is more important than another criterion, then it should take a score between 2 and 9, depending on how much more important it is compared to the other criterion, with 9 indicating that is much more important.

Please indicate your preference between two criteria by providing your preference between 1 and 9

Number	Scale
9	Extremely preferred
8	Very strong to extremely preferred
7	Very strong preferred
6	Strongly to very strongly preferred
5	Strongly preferred
4	Moderately to strongly preferred
3	Moderately preferred
2	Equally to moderately preferred
1	Equally preferred

OBU: On-Board Unit

MEC: Multi-access Edge Computing

Which of the following do you consider more important?

H/W resources (OBUs)

✖ Reset

Virtualised Application Functions / Network Functions

H/W resources (OBUs)

✖ Reset

H/W resources (MEC)

Virtualised Application Functions / Network Functions

✖ Reset

H/W resources (MEC)

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Figure 32: Comparison of resources section

Comparison of support options

5G-IANA project has identified the following Support options as the most important for the AOEP:

- Support by email / on-line form
- Ticketing System
- Webinars / Videos (Interactive)
- Training by experts

Please answer the questions using the following instructions:

Each criterion will be rated according to its degree of relative importance to the other criteria within the group using pair wise comparisons to rank them. Please indicate your preference between two criteria by providing your preference between 1 and 9.

When two criteria are of equal importance, they should take a score of 1. When one criterion is more important than another criterion, then it should take a score between 2 and 9, depending on how much more important it is compared to the other criterion, with 9 indicating that is much more important.

Please indicate your preference between two criteria by providing your preference between 1 and 9

Number	Scale
9	Extremely preferred
8	Very strong to extremely preferred
7	Very strong preferred
6	Strongly to very strongly preferred
5	Strongly preferred
4	Moderately to strongly preferred
3	Moderately preferred
2	Equally to moderately preferred
1	Equally preferred

Which of the following do you consider more important?

Support by email / on-line form

Ticketing system

Support by email / on-line form

Webinars/videos (interactive)

Support by email / on-line form

Training by experts

Ticketing system

Webinars/videos (interactive)

Ticketing system

Training by experts

Webinars/videos (interactive)

Training by experts

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Figure 33: Comparison of support section

Expectations from 5G-IANA platform

***How important are you considering the following use cases for the automotive sector?**

	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
Hazard Notification (e.g., high-risk driving detection)	<input type="radio"/>				
Vehicle movement (e.g., remote driving)	<input type="radio"/>				
Infotainment (e.g., in-vehicle VR, AR applications)	<input type="radio"/>				
Vertical-agnostic (e.g., network status monitoring, predictive Quality of Service)	<input type="radio"/>				

***How important are the following resources for running your experiment in the 5G-IANA platform?**

	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
Storage	<input type="radio"/>				
RAM	<input type="radio"/>				
CPUs	<input type="radio"/>				
GPUs	<input type="radio"/>				

What are your expectations regarding 5G network performance (please provide the minimum required value)

- Round-trip time:** the time duration between the transmission of a message from a network node and the successful reception of the response message by the same point
- UL rate:** the upload rate experienced by the user
- DL rate:** the download rate experienced by the user
- Reliability:** one minus packets loss rate

Round Trip Time (ms)

UL user rate (Mbps)

DL user rate (Mbps)

Reliability (%)

Please provide details about any required (far edge) resources for running your experiment in the 5G-IANA AOEP

Min number of vehicles/OBUs

***Provide an estimate regarding the time you would require to execute and test your experiment in the 5G-IANA platform**

Choose one of the following answers

1 day or less

2-3 days

1 week

More that a week

Other:

Figure 34: Expectations section (part 1)

*** How useful do you consider the following data/code to be open for you?**

	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
Datasets from already conducted use cases on the 5G-IANA platform	<input type="radio"/>				
Virtual Application or Network Functions	<input type="radio"/>				
Evaluation data (results from conducted experiments on the platform)	<input type="radio"/>				
Application monitoring data	<input type="radio"/>				
Network monitoring data	<input type="radio"/>				
Local resources monitoring data	<input type="radio"/>				

*** How important do you consider the following aspects of the 5G-IANA platform?**

	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
Ease of onboarding your Virtual Application on Network Functions /NetApps	<input type="radio"/>				
Low service creation time	<input type="radio"/>				

*** How important are the following parameters to be defined for your NetApps through the User Interface (UI) of the 5G-IANA platform?**

	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
Determine the network location of AF/NF (cloud/ edge / far edge)	<input type="radio"/>				
Determine the geographic location of targeted OBU's	<input type="radio"/>				
Determine high level networking KPIs that should be met for certain AF (delay, bandwidth, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
Selection of targeted KPIs to be monitored	<input type="radio"/>				

*** How familiar are you with the following concepts:**

	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
FLOWER Federated Learning Framework	<input type="radio"/>				
Older radio systems (LTE)	<input type="radio"/>				
NetApps	<input type="radio"/>				
5G	<input type="radio"/>				

*** How essential would the monitoring of the following Service level KPIs be for the successful experimentation of your Use Case?**

i

- E2E Latency is the maximum accepted latency across the entire service chain (of a UC).
- E2E Reliability is defined as the percentage of correctly received packets over the total packets transmitted in the complete service chain.
- Service Availability is the percentage of time that an application is accessible and usable within a predefined QoS level e.g., the fraction of time a software component is functional (up) or the fraction of requests that are serviced correctly.
- Application Jitter is the statistical variation of the end-to-end latency for the communications across the entire service chain of the vertical service.
- Quality of Experience (QoE) is defined as the overall acceptability of an application or service, as perceived subjectively by the end-user.
- Prediction Accuracy in classification tasks is a measure of how well an algorithm correctly identifies or excludes a condition i.e., the proportion of correct predictions among the total number of cases examined.
- Service Deployment time: the duration required for setting up E2E logical services characterized by respective network level guarantees (such as bandwidth, end-to-end latency, reliability, etc.).

	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
E2E Latency	<input type="radio"/>				
E2E Reliability	<input type="radio"/>				
Service Availability	<input type="radio"/>				
Application Jitter	<input type="radio"/>				
Quality of Experience (QoE)	<input type="radio"/>				
Algorithm Prediction Accuracy	<input type="radio"/>				
Service deployment time	<input type="radio"/>				

Figure 35: Expectations section (part 2)

***How essential would the monitoring of the following Network level KPIs be for the successful experimentation of your Use Case?**

Round-trip time: the time duration between the transmission of a message from a network node and the successful reception of the response message by the same point

- UL rate: the upload rate experienced by the user
- DL rate: the download rate experienced by the user
- Reliability: one minus packets loss rate

	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
Round-trip time (RTT)	<input type="radio"/>				
UL (DL) user data rate	<input type="radio"/>				
UL (DL) packet loss rate	<input type="radio"/>				
Reliability	<input type="radio"/>				

***As part of the 5G-IANA project, an Open Call will be opened for SMEs, which will aim to invite third parties with their network applications so as to run them on top of the platform provided by the project, making use of 5G connectivity. The Open Call will take place in 2 phases, with the first starting in early 2023, and the second towards the end of 2023, and will award 3 prizes of 15K each to 3 selected SMEs.**

Are you willing to participate in the Open Call?

Choose one of the following answers

Yes

No

Maybe

If you would like to be informed with more information regarding the 5G-IANA open call please provide your email adress

***What would be the purpose of experimentation with the 5G-IANA platform?**

Choose one of the following answers

Testing of an application using 5G

Developing a new product

Developing a new NF/AF/NetApp

Research purposes

Interest on the business model etc.

Other:

If you would like to be informed with more information regarding the 5G-IANA open call please provide your email adress

Do you consider any other aspect as important that was not covered by the survey? If yes please elaborate:

Provide more details about any potential experiment that you would like to run in the 5G-IANA platform or describe your network applications

Figure 36: Expectations section (part 3)

APPENDIX II – DETAILED RESULTS

Figure 37: Importance of Hazard Notification UC

Figure 38: Importance of Remote Driving UC

Figure 39: Importance of Infotainment UC

Figure 40: Importance of Vertical agnostic UC

Figure 41: Importance of Storage

Figure 42: Importance of RAM

Figure 43: Importance of CPUs

Figure 44: Importance of GPUs

Figure 45: Open data (Datasets from already conducted use cases on the 5G-IANA platform)

Figure 46: Open data (Virtual Application or Network Functions)

Figure 47: Open data (Evaluation data (results from conducted experiments on the platform))

Figure 48: Open data (Application monitoring data)

Figure 49: Open data (Network monitoring data)

Figure 50: Open data (Local resources monitoring data)

How important do you consider the following aspects of the 5G-IANA platform? (Ease of onboarding your Virtual Application on Network Functions /nApps)

Figure 51: Importance of different aspects (onboarding ease)

How important do you consider the following aspects of the 5G-IANA platform? (Low service creation time)

Figure 52: Importance of different aspects (service creation time)

Figure 53: Determine the network location of AF/NF from UI

Figure 54: Determine the geographic location of OBUs from UI

How important are the following parameters to be defined for your nApps through the User Interface (UI) of the 5G-IANA platform?
 (Determine high level networking KPIs that should be met for certain AF (delay, bandwidth, etc.))

Figure 55: Determine high level networking KPIs from UI

How important are the following parameters to be defined for your nApps through the User Interface (UI) of the 5G-IANA platform?
 (Selection of targeted KPIs to be monitored)

Figure 56: Select targeted KPIs from UI

Figure 57: Familiarity with FLOWER framework

Figure 58: Familiarity with LTE

Figure 59: Familiarity with nApps

Figure 60: Familiarity with 5G

Figure 61: Monitoring of service level KPIs (E2E latency)

Figure 62: Monitoring of service level KPIs (E2E reliability)

Figure 63: Monitoring of service level KPIs (Service reliability)

Figure 64: Monitoring of service level KPIs (Application Jitter)

Figure 65: Monitoring of service level KPIs (QoE)

Figure 66: Monitoring of service level KPIs (Algorithm Prediction Accuracy)

Figure 67: Monitoring of service level KPIs (Service deployment time)

Figure 68: Monitoring of network level KPIs (RTT)

Figure 69: Monitoring of network level KPIs (User data rate)

Figure 70: Monitoring of network level KPIs (packet loss rate)

Figure 71: Monitoring of network level KPIs (reliability)